
Analysis of the Application of the Capital Asset Pricing Model (CAPM) Method to Final Decision in Share Investment

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ABSTRACT

Investment is delaying or reducing consumption at present in order to get benefits in the future. This activity requires a significant investment (long-term financing). Before making an investment decision, investors must conduct a review first. The benefits of this research are not only for making a decision on several investment instruments, but also related to company assets. Given the increasing interest of investors in investing, to avoid investment failure it is necessary to conduct research on investment decisions through the 'capital price model and rate of change in the method of return. Therefore, researchers took the initiative to conduct the same research. The reason for choosing shares listed on the LQ45 index is because the stocks listed in the LQ45 index are stocks that have high liquidity on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX). In other words, shares listed on the LQ45 index are stocks that are actively traded on the stock market. Of course, this determines potential investors because these shares are active stocks. From this research, there are three under-valued stocks from 5 samples that are worth buying by investors.

1. INTRODUCTION

A country's economic growth is one indicator of a country's success (Santosa Putra et al. 2020). One of the efforts that must be made by a country to achieve this is by increasing investment activities (Kusuma and Shulthoni 2021a). Investment is delaying or reducing consumption at present in order to get benefits in the future (Pratama, Purnamawati, and Sayekti 2019). This activity requires a significant investment (long-term financing). Before making an investment decision, investors must conduct a review first (Febryanti, Sayekti, and Agustini 2020). The benefits of this research are not only for making a decision on several investment instruments, but also related to company assets (Roziq, Sulistiyo, et al. 2020).

According to Law no. 8 Capital Market Law, the capital market is an activity related to securities trading, state-owned enterprises associated with securities issuance, related agencies, and businesses (Nuha, Miqdad, and Sulistiyo 2021). This means that the capital market in Indonesia is established as a vehicle for investors (investors) with companies or government agencies (Afifi, Kustono, and Nuha 2022). Investors are parties who have excess funds, while companies or government institutions need funds to fund ongoing or future projects through investment activities (Luthfiyatul Farida, Roziq, and Maria Wardayati 2019).

In investing, there are three factors that need to be considered, namely the expected rate of return, the level of risk and the availability of

investment (Tandelilin 2010). Investors expect high returns on certain risks (Kustono, Agustini, and Dermawan 2021). Thus, investors can take direct decisions on investment without calculations and arguments (Kustono, Roziq, and Nanggala 2021). Because the main objective of investing is to generate a significant return from a certain risk (Irmadariyani et al. 2019).

To create an effective investment portfolio, the key is to consider the potential risk or uncertainty that will come and identify the expected return and determine the level of risk that will be borne by each investor (Purnamawati et al. 2019a). When evaluating what is considered the most targeted return and risk, the CAPM (Rate of Return Variation) method and the RVAR (Rate of Return Variation) method are used to assess the potential investment in stocks (Kuncorowati, Miqdad, and Roziq 2021a).

The CAPM method assesses the effectiveness of a portfolio consisting of stocks (Prasetyo et al. 2020). Sharpe (1966) offers a variable ratio or portfolio presentation dimension, which is commonly called the Sharpe Measure. The RVAR method measures the effectiveness of a stock portfolio by dividing the excess R by the reduction in the security index, and then determining the standard deviation by arranging the order of selection the main protection for the portfolio (Putri, Miqdad, and Sulistiyo 2020a).

Given the increasing interest of investors in investing, to avoid investment failure it is necessary to conduct research on investment decisions through the 'capital price model and rate of change in the method of return (Purnamawati et al. 2019b). Therefore, researchers took the initiative to conduct the same research (Agus Winarno et al. 2021a). The reason for choosing shares listed on the LQ45 index is because the stocks listed in the LQ45 index are stocks that have high liquidity on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) (Ely, Effendi, and Mas'ud 2019). In other words, shares listed on the LQ45 index are stocks that are actively traded on the stock market (A. Roziq, Marizca, and Kustono 2021). Of course, this determines potential investors because these shares are active stocks.

In addition, the researcher hopes that the basis of this study can test whether there are

stocks that are suitable for investment in stocks listed on the LQ45 index (Putri, Miqdad, and Sulistiyo 2020b). Based on infrastructure and according to previous research, the researchers named it "Analyzing the Application of How to Make Money". The final model of capital decision making (CAPM) for financing (analysis of companies listed in LQ45 Index from February 2020 to July 2020).

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK AND HYPOTHESES

Investment Decision

The investment decision is related to the decision whether to buy or sell stock (Farida, Roziq, and Wardayati 2019). The decision to sell or buy shares can be based on stock price, stock return, stock excess return, (Samsul 2006). Basically, to decide whether to sell or buy is necessary it is known whether the stock position is undervalued (said to be cheap) or overvalued (said to be expensive) (Agus Winarno et al. 2021b).

Investors' decisions to sell and buy are inseparable from the characteristics of these investors (Ahmad Roziq et al. 2021). Type of investor can tolerate risk can be divided into 3, namely risk seekers who like risk even though it is risk it can be greater than the returns it gets (Pratiwi, Maharani, and Sayekti 2021). Then the investor neutral which chooses the amount of risk that is balanced with the returns acquired (Hadi, Wardayati, and Miqdad 2020). Then the last one is the risk averse investor who is still can tolerate small risks, does not mean unwilling to accept or avoiding risk (Manurung 2009).

CAPM

The CAPM model was introduced by Treynor, Sharpe, and Lintner is a development of the portfolio theory proposed by Markowitz by introducing new terms namely systematic risk and specific risk or unsystematic risk (A. Roziq, Zumaroh, et al. 2021). In 1990, William Sharpe won the Nobel Prize in economics for the theory of financial asset price formation then called the Capital Asset Pricing Model (Naftali 2009).

(Bodie et al. 2006) explained that CAPM is the main result of modern financial economy.

The Capital Asset Pricing Model (CAPM) provides precise prediction between the risk of an asset and the level of expectation expected return (Hidayatullah, Wardayati, and Roziq 2021). This model explains that the rate of return what is expected is the sum of the risk-free return assets and risk premium (Miqdad and Oktaviani 2021). The risk premium is calculated from beta multiplied by premium expected market risk (Kuncorowati, Miqdad, and Roziq 2021b). The market risk premium is calculated from the rate of return the expected market is reduced by risk-free return on assets (Winarno, Mas'ud, and Palupi 2021).

Stock Return

Stock return is the level of profit enjoyed by investors or investors for an investment they do (Wulandari, Maharani, and Wardhaningrum 2021). Returns received by investors depend on the investment instruments they buy or transact (Kusuma and Shulthoni 2021c).

In (Jogiyanto 1998), return it-self is the result obtained from investment in the form of realized return and return expected return. Realized return is the return that has been occurs which is calculated based on historical data which is used as wrong a measure of company performance (Sulistiyo, al Ardi, and Roziq 2020). Return realization is the basis of determination of expected return (Roziq, Wijayanti, and Irmadariyani 2020). Meanwhile, the expected return is the return which is expected to occur in the future which is uncertain (Suyitno, Miqdad, and Sayekti 2020).

In investing, the return is calculated using the total return (Jogiyanto 2003). Total return is the overall return of investment in a certain period (Kusuma and Shulthoni 2021b). Total return consists of capital gains (loss) and yield. Capital gain (loss) is the difference in profit (loss) from the price investment now, relative to prices for the past period (Ardianne, Sulistiyo, and Roziq 2020). Capital gain is very depending on the market price of the relevant investment instrument that the investment instrument must be traded in the market (Wardhaningrum and Kartika 2020). Because with trading, there will be changes in the value of an instrument investment. While the yield is the percentage of dividends against the stock price the previous

period (Sri Kustono 2021).

3. RESEARCH METHOD

This research is a research that uses a quantitative method which is presented in the form of a descriptive explanation, in which the researcher uses the Capital Asset Pricing Model (CAPM) method in this study to determine which types of stocks are classified as cheap or undervalued and expensive or overvalued, based on returns and risks as evaluation materials. Investors in determining the decisions to be taken in investing in stocks (Khasanah, Roziq, and Sulistiyo 2021).

In this study, researchers used several company stocks listed in the LQ45 index on the Indonesia Stock Exchange from August 2020 to July 2020. This study uses secondary data sourced from the IDX website, Bank Indonesia website and Yahoo Finance website.

The variables used to support this research are individual stock returns (Ri), market returns (Rm), risk-free returns (Rf), systematic risk (β), expected returns [E (Ri)]. Sampling was done by random sampling. The number of samples taken at random were 5 company stocks.

Table 1. Research Samples of Companies Listed in the LQ45 Index for the period February 2020 to July 2020

No.	Code
1.	ANTM
2.	BTPS
3.	ERAA
4.	SCMA
5.	UNVR

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

In this study, it discusses how the application of the CAPM method is used to determine the types of stocks that are included in the cheap or undervalued and expensive or overvalued categories, based on stock returns and their risks.

Individual Stock Return (Ri)

The results of processing research data regarding the calculation of the rate of return on

individual shares in the period February 2020 - July 2020, show that Unilever Indonesia Tbk. (UNVR) had the largest return of 0.1958 or 19.58%, and the stock with the smallest return was Erajaya Swasembada Tbk. (ERAA) of -0.3324 or -33.24%.

Table 2. Return of Individual Shares for the Period of February 2020 to July 2020

No.	Code	R _i
1.	ANTM	0,1735
2.	BTPS	-0,3257
3.	ERAA	-0,3324
4.	SCMA	0,0292
5.	UNVR	0,1958

Source: Data Processed, 2020

Market Return (R_m)

The results of processing research data regarding the calculation of the market rate of return in the period February 2020 - July 2020, show that the largest market return was in July 2020 of 0.049790129 or 4.97%, and the smallest market return was in March 2020 of -0,167581198 or -16.75%.

Table 3. Market Return for the Period of February 2020 to July 2020

Months	IHSG	R _m
February	5.452,70	-0,082044764
March	4.538,93	-0,167581198
April	4.716,40	0,039099523
May	4.753,61	0,007889492
June	4.905,39	0,031929418
July	5.149,63	0,049790129
Total		-0,1209174
Average		-0,0201529

Source: Data Processed, 2020

Risk Free Return (R_f)

The results of processing research data regarding the calculation of risk-free returns in the period February 2020 - July 2020, show the

highest risk-free return in July 2020, while the lowest risk-free return is in February 2020.

Table 4. Risk Free Return for the Period of February 2020 to July 2020

Months	Year	SBI/R _f
February	2020	4,75%
March	2020	4,50%
April	2020	4,50%
May	2020	4,50%
June	2020	4,25%
July	2020	4,00%

Source: Data Processed, 2020

Systematic Risk (β)

The results of processing research data regarding systematic risk calculations in the period February 2020 - July from 5 companies used as research samples, show that the highest beta (β) is found at Bank BTPN Syariah Tbk (BTPS), which is 3,750252982, this is because (β) > 1 which means having the highest risk, the smallest beta (β) is found at Unilever Indonesia Tbk. (UNVR) is -0.128933341, this is because the beta value (β) < 1 means that it has the lowest risk.

Table 5. Systematic Risk (β) Companies Registered with LQ45 for the Period February 2020 to July 2020

No.	Code	Beta (β)
1.	ANTM	1,906699902
2.	BTPS	3,750252982
3.	ERAA	1,28569826
4.	SCMA	2,373875631
5.	UNVR	0,128933341

Source: Data Processed, 2020

Expected Return [E (R_i)]

The results of the researcher's data processing regarding the calculation of expected returns in the period February 2020 - July from 5 companies used as research samples, show Aneka Tambang Tbk. (ANTM) has the largest expected return, namely 0.009104 or 0.91%. Meanwhile, the smallest expected return is found in Surya

Citra Media Tbk (SCMA) of 0.00583 or 0.58%.

Table 6. Expected Return for the Period of February 2020 to July 2020

No.	Code	E(R _i)
1.	ANTM	0.009104
2.	BTPS	0.008863
3.	ERAA	0.005889
4.	SCMA	0.005839
5.	UNVR	0.008120

Source: Data Processed, 2020

Table 7. Undervalued and Overvalued

No.	Code	Value	Decisions
1.	ANTM	Undervalued	Buy shares
2.	BTPS	Overvalued	Selling shares
3.	ERAA	Overvalued	Selling shares
4.	SCMA	Undervalued	Buy shares
5.	UNVR	Undervalued	Buy shares

Source: Data Processed, 2020

Stock is undervalued or called cheap if $(R_i) > E(R_i)$, whereas if $(R_i) < E(R_i)$ is said to be expensive or overvalued.

5. CONCLUSION, IMPLICATION, SUGGESTION, AND LIMITATIONS

Based on the results and discussion above, of the 5 sample companies it shows that Unilever Indonesia Tbk. (UNVR) had the largest return, namely 0.1958 or 19.58%. Shares that have the highest beta (β) are the highest beta (β) found in Bank BTPN Syariah Tbk (BTPS), which is 3,750252982, this is because $(\beta) > 1$ means having the highest risk, and shares with Aneka Tambang Tbk. (ANTM) has the largest expected return, namely 0.009104 or 0.91%. There are 3 company shares that are included in the undervalued or cheap category, namely shares of ANTM, SCMA, and UNVR.

Suggestions from researchers based on the results of this study are: 1) Investors who will do stocks should use the CAPM method to find out which stocks are in the cheap or undervalued category and the expensive or overvalued category. 2) For further researchers, it is expected to use a different sample in the CAPM method because it aims to expand knowledge about the CAPM method.

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